

NEED FOR SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN EMPOWERING WOMEN: A ROLE OF SKILL INDIA MISSION

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to assess and investigate the necessity of skill development and how it helps women become more powerful. Women are seen as an economic asset in every community and play an important role in their social, cultural, economic, and religious lifestyles. However, they continue to fall well short in many areas of life, including work, education, health, and economic empowerment, among others. Despite their diligence, they have little control over resources and economic activity. Therefore, in order to remove inequality, discrimination, and exploitation and to accomplish women's overall growth in society, skill development is necessary to enable economic empowerment of women. Women have been excluded from the amazing advancement of humanity due to a lack of education and skill development. Skill development among women is the need of the hour so as to make them confident, self-reliant and to develop in them the ability to be a part of decision making. Women can live with dignity and independence if they are empowered via education and skill development. The Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) has been carrying out a number of programs to empower women via skill development. Through ten programs in skill development and entrepreneurship, the Skill India Mission seeks to empower women and boost their participation in the workforce.

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Introduction:

Women are crucial to the growth of families and societies. They have been actively involved in a variety of social and economic activities for the past few decades, yet their efforts are still unacknowledged. They continue to face prejudice in the social, economic, and educational spheres in this male-dominated country. In addition to taking care of their families, women are crucial to the advancement of society as a whole. A key concern is educating women about their rights and boosting their self-esteem. It takes a lot of work to develop a trained labor force in order to establish economic prosperity. In the case of women, the goal of skill development is not just to get them ready for the workforce but also to improve the quality of the work they do. One can see that there is still a long way to go when considering the significance of women's contributions to a country's growth. A person's total growth is greatly influenced by their education and skill development, which helps them become more conscious, understand their social, political, and cultural surroundings better, and improve their socioeconomic circumstances.

Meaning of Women Empowerment and Components:

According to Tam O'Neil: Women's empowerment is a process of personal and social change through which they gain power, meaningful choices and control their lives. According to UN definition women's empowerment has Five Components:

- Women's sense of self worth
- Right to have and determine choice
- Right to have access to opportunities and resource
- Right to have control on their own lives both within and outside the home
- Ability to help the direction of social change to create more social and economic order, nationally and internationally.

Skill India Mission Empowers Women in Skill Development and Entrepreneurship:

Through ten initiatives in skill development and entrepreneurship, the Skill India mission empowers women. The following programs are started to help women enhance their skills and encourage entrepreneurship.

Long Term Skill Development Training via Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs): Over 22.82 lakh applicants have been recruited (in one-year and two-year trades) through a vast network of 15,042 ITIs across the nation, with a particular emphasis on the enrollment of women. The number of female trainees admitted in 2018 increased by about 97% from 87,799 in 2014 to 173,105. Women only receive skill training in 18 National Skill Training Institutes (for Women). Additionally, all Centrally Funded Institutes (CFIs) have launched special batches under the National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS) to give women theoretical and fundamental training. Under the Craftsmen Training Scheme (CTS) and Craft Instructors' Training Scheme (CITS), the NSTIs (W) offer NCVT-approved skill training programs in a number of fields, including office management, electronics, fashion design and technology, computer-aided embroidery and design, etc.

Short Term Skill Development Training: Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana, the Ministry's flagship program, aims to enhance women's employment participation through gender mainstreaming and suitable skill development. Out of the 56 lakh candidates who have benefited from the program, women make up about half of those enrolled and trained under PMKVY. The industry's needs for female experts are taken into consideration since employment positions are continuously revised to reflect market need. In addition to teaching women employable skills, the Skill India Mission's programs are tailored to their requirements by offering childcare assistance, flexible scheduling, and safe transportation.

Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL): More than 4 lakh female candidates have received training in a variety of skill areas under the Recognition of Prior Learning (RPL) program, which recognizes their current abilities with a formal certificate and

provides them with a way to improve their standard of living.

Apprenticeship Training: Apprentices now have more options in the service industry thanks to the extensive changes made to the Apprenticeship Act of 1961. During 50,000 women in seven states and UTs would benefit from a targeted pilot program run by Skill India through NSDC in collaboration with UNDP and the Society of Development Alternatives (DA) during a 15-month period. The Directorate General of Training, a division of MSDE, is conducting a gender study to identify barriers to women's participation in ITI and apprenticeship training as well as their entry into the workforce in order to further promote apprenticeship training.

Apprenticeship Training: The goal of the National Skill Development and Policy is to improve economic productivity by increasing women's participation in inclusive skill development. In order to accomplish this, emphasis has been placed on developing more infrastructure for women's training and apprenticeship; flexible training delivery methods, such as mobile training units, flexible afternoon batches, and local need-based training to accommodate women; and guaranteeing a safe and gender-sensitive training environment, hiring female trainers, equitable compensation, and a complaint reprisal mechanism. Sectors that are anticipated to have a higher proportion of women in the workforce have also been identified by the skill gap surveys.

Special Women Centric Projects: NSDC focuses solely on the skill development of women, particularly in rural regions, through its training partners, including the Mann Deshi Foundation, Shri Mahila Sewa Sahkari Bank Limited, and Sri Sarada Math Rasik Bhita. To make it easier for them to start their own firm, the training consists of teaching digital, accounting, and entrepreneurial skills. In partnership with the Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation, NSDC is also promoting the skill development of workers for the Swachh Bharat Mission. These jobs include training masonry for twin pit toilets and gobar gas (biofuel), where women have been encouraged to participate.

Partnerships with Private and Non-Government Organizations to Skill Development: Organizations like Airbnb, which assist home stay services by offering training in the hospitality

and tourism sectors, are among the cooperative efforts with private actors. Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham is focusing on rural areas as part of a PMKVY project to promote women's empowerment through skill development and the establishment of job possibilities. The project is aimed at the tribal population and other neglected and vulnerable groups.

Projects in Pradhan Mantri Mahila Kaushal Kendra (PMMKK): More than 6000 training goals have recently been set aside to train women in four PMMKs. In order to help new mothers engage in skill training, many organizations also offer a crèche. Self-employed tailors, beauty therapists, customer service representatives, hair stylists, yoga instructors, and others are receiving training.

Future Jobs and Industry Oriented Courses: Nearly 450 occupational opportunities that are focused on women's skill development are in line with NSQF. In addition to seeing a rise in women's engagement in hard skills like welding and vehicle repair, Skill India is promoting women's participation in cutting-edge jobs related to Industry 4.0, such as artificial intelligence, 3D printing, data analytics, etc.

Entrepreneurial Initiatives: MSDE is dedicated to supporting the nation's female entrepreneurs. The goal of NIESBUD's Entrepreneurship Development Programs for rural women under the MSDE is to instill in them the entrepreneurial ideals, mindset, and drive to take on the obstacles of starting their own businesses or group enterprises. The Institute also uses the Livelihood Business Incubation (LBI) approach to support female entrepreneurs.

Findings:

According to the report, the government and its agency partners have implemented the skill development system for women in a number of ways. Women's empowerment has been greatly impacted by skill development. The perception of women in the workforce has been altered. The outcomes are: They began their little businesses with a respectable salary. Women's employment in the organized sector has grown by 12%. They can now present, communicate, and analyze with ease thanks to employable skills. The number of women entrepreneurs in the nation has increased as

a result of skill development.

Discussion:

It is crucial to understand and research the need for skill development because women make up a sizable portion of the population that has been deprived and backward for decades and whose contribution to the country's development has been duly acknowledged by the government. However, the reality is that women's access to skills still lags behind in comparison to other groups. Talk is necessary to make things better.

To Support This:

- More seats for women must be created in order to enhance policies for them.
- Digital platforms can be utilized to empower women.
- They would have greater options to make a living and become independent if they were empowered through skill-building programs.
- Training policies must be created with gender views and an awareness of regional traditions and customs.
- Increase the number of training facilities in isolated locations that offer job prospects for sustainable

Conclusion:

In order to solve some of the most pressing issues pertaining to addition, gender equality, and access, skill development and training will be essential. The development of skills is aided by education. Skills: Currently, India can develop the skills of over 3.1 million people annually. According to the eleventh five-year plan, which capacity will rise to 15 million per year. India wants to produce 500 million trained workers by 2027; therefore skill development programs must be more capable.

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